

The Delay of the Cortilymph-Wave from Scale-Fluid-Basilar-Membrane Traveling Wave is shaped by the Outer-Hair-Cell RC Time Constant

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Abstract. Many aspects of cochlear physiology are different between the high-frequency base and the low-frequency apex. In the base, recent data show that amplification of the traveling wave does not come from outer-hair-cell (OHC) forces acting on the basilar membrane (BM). Instead, it is hypothesized to come from OHCs producing cyclic cortilymph flow along the organ-of-Corti (OoC) tunnels, which changes OoC area and adds energy to the scala-fluid traveling wave. One origin of cochlear base-to-apex differences is the OHC-membrane RC filter that changes the delay between OHC-stereocilia current and the resulting OHC voltage. Measurements in live animals have shown the OHC-RC corner frequency, F_c , is ~ 3 kHz. At tone frequencies $\gg F_c$, the RC delay provides the correct timing for OoC-area-change traveling-wave amplification. However, at frequencies $\ll F_c$, the RC delay is small, and the cortilymph-flow wave occurs earlier relative to the scala-fluid+BM wave. This produces a separation between the two fluid waves in the apex: the scala-fluid+BM traveling wave and the cortilymph wave, with the cortilymph wave having a shorter delay. Auditory-nerve (AN) fiber delays and rate-saturations are consistent with the hypothesis that AN fibers are excited at low levels by both waves, in tuning-curve edges (or “side lobes”) by the cortilymph wave, and at high levels by the passive part of the scala-fluid+BM wave. The change at F_c in the slope of SFOAE delay versus frequency data is due, in part, to the advance at F_c of the cortilymph wave relative to the scala-fluid+BM wave, but other factors are also involved.

INTRODUCTION

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) has led to a revolution in understanding cochlear motion and cochlear amplification. Amplification of motion is no longer restricted to the basilar membrane (BM) at the best frequency (BF) and $\frac{1}{2}$ octave below BF, but is found in many organ-of-Corti (OoC) structures and extends far below BF^{1,2}. Significantly, OCT data from high-frequency regions show that the motions at the tops and bottoms of the outer hair cells (OHCs) are at the wrong relative phase to amplify the traveling wave by OHC forces acting on the BM³⁻⁵. Instead, it has been proposed that OHCs amplify traveling waves by cyclically changing the local OoC cross-section area, thereby increasing cyclic reticular lamina (RL) motion, which acts on and amplifies the scala-media-fluid traveling wave³⁻⁵. The OoC area change is produced by cortilymph flowing from where OHCs contract and force fluid into and along the cochlear tunnels, to where OHCs expand and cortilymph flows back to around the OHCs; these points are separated by $\lambda/2$ (λ is the traveling-wave wavelength). Cortilymph flow out of an OoC cross-section and into the tunnels of adjacent cross-sections decreases the local cross-section area. The resulting change in OoC area, acting against the stiff BM, puts force on the scala-media fluid at the correct phase to add energy to the fluid traveling wave³⁻⁵. As the fluid-wave moves apically, the amplified trans-partition pressure difference increases the apical BM motion, i.e., BM motion is amplified indirectly. An important aspect of the area-change hypothesis is that the cortilymph flow is large only when the flow distance is short, i.e., where λ is short. A simple model shows that having the impedance that opposes the cortilymph flow be approximately proportional to λ , causes the flow to become large where λ is small, which allows OHC length changes to produce OoC area changes only in the short-wave region near BF⁶.

This cortilymph-flow, area-change mechanism explains how OHC motility produces traveling-wave amplification focused only near BF, but it is based on evidence from high-BF basal regions and is not expected to hold for low-BF apical regions (in this paper “apex” refers only to the apex in animals that have BFs <1 kHz). Example base-to-apex differences are: 1. In the base, auditory-nerve (AN) tuning curves (TCs) are narrow and V-shaped with a high-level, low-frequency tail, while in the apex TCs are wider and sometimes have low-to-moderate-level side-lobes⁷. 2. Low-frequency tones excite AN fibers at one phase in the base and at the opposite phase in the apex (e.g.⁸). 3. The group delays of otoacoustic emissions (OAEs) as functions of stimulus frequency show high- and low-frequency regions with a slope-change near the middle of the cochlea^{9,10}.

WHAT CAUSES BASE-TO-APEX DIFFERENCES?

Almost all aspects of cochlear anatomy diverge from base to apex, including BM width, BM stiffness, the tilts re the BM of the OHCs and RL, OoC cell sizes, and the fluid-space sizes. While these anatomical divergences must have roles in base-to-apex physiological differences, most are gradual, and no anatomical divergence has an obvious relationship to the base-to-apex differences. Here it is proposed that an important source of base-to-apex differences is the phase change produced by the OHC-membrane RC filter. At frequencies far *above* the RC corner frequency (F_c), stereocilia current produces a change in OHC voltage that lags the current by $\frac{1}{4}$ cycle¹¹. In contrast, at frequencies far *below* F_c , the change in OHC voltage is at almost the same phase as the current. F_c has been measured in isolated OHCs, but such measurements are unlikely to represent F_c in an intact cochlea¹². Measurements of F_c in intact, sensitive gerbils concluded that $F_c \sim 3$ kHz¹², which matches well with the cochlear high-to-low-transition frequency.

Why would the OHC-RC phase make a big difference? Because sets the phase relationship for producing traveling-wave amplification. In high-BF cochlear regions, BM motion is transmitted by stiff pillar cells and produces an almost simultaneous deflection of OHC stereocilia, but the OHC-RC filter causes the OHC voltage change, and therefore somatic motility, to lag BM motion by $\sim \frac{1}{4}$ cycle. For OHC forces to add energy by acting on the BM, this delay makes the OHC motion be at the wrong phase: during half of the cycle, motion at the bottom of the OHCs is in the same direction as BM motion, but in the other half of the cycle the motions are in the opposite directions¹⁻⁵. In contrast, at the top of the OHC, the RL (plus tectorial membrane (TM)) motion is *in phase* with the change in scala-media (SM) fluid pressure, and thus can *add energy to the fluid traveling wave*³⁻⁵. In this high-frequency mechanism for traveling-wave amplification, the OHC time constant provides a necessary $\frac{1}{4}$ cycle phase lag. However, at frequencies far below F_c , the OHC-RC phase lag is not present, so the RL motion is at the wrong phase for adding energy to the fluid traveling wave. Far below F_c , OHC motion is at the correct phase for adding energy *by acting on the BM*, and this may be a source of traveling-wave amplification. However, this may not be the whole story for low-BF traveling-wave amplification because in the low-BF cochlear apex, the OHC long axis is closer to parallel to the BM, instead of perpendicular as would seem preferable for OHC length changes to act on BM transverse motion.

To understand the effects of the OHC-RC time constant, it is useful to visualize how it can affect the phase relationships of the waves along the cochlea. Our explanation for traveling wave amplification postulates that OHC action produces cortilymph flow into and along the OoC tunnels⁴⁻⁶. The phase relationships of the scala-fluid+BM traveling wave and the cortilymph-flow wave are illustrated in Figure 1 (Although the traveling wave is often thought of as carried by the BM, its energy is carried by the scala fluid, not the BM. Considering this, and that traveling-wave amplification is hypothesized to be produced by adding energy to the SM fluid motion, we use the term “scala-fluid+BM” instead of just “BM” traveling wave).

In Figure 1, as a marker of the phase of cortilymph flow we have used the point of greatest flow of cortilymph from around the OHCs and into the tunnels, which has the advantage for illustration of being at approximately the same phase as peak BM motion (see Fig. 3 in⁶). Figure 1 diagrams the length of a chinchilla cochlea and, at seven sample frequencies, shows snapshots of traveling waves in their peak regions (calculated from the propagation and gain functions in Fig. 9 of¹³). Figure 1 shows that the scala-fluid+BM and cortilymph waves are synchronized in high-BF regions but are $\frac{1}{4}$ period out-of-phase in low-BF regions. The region with the greatest change in phase with distance along the cochlea is at F_c (3 kHz) which fits with the typical location of the apical-basal transition. Considering the common view that the basal-to-apical transition occurs over a narrow frequency region, the change along the cochlea produced by the OHC RC filter is slower than might be expected for the cause of the transition. It may be that the apical and basal mechanisms of cochlear amplification still work well enough when the phase change from the ideal values is small, but work poorly when the change is near $\frac{1}{8}$ period (i.e., near 3 kHz), which would concentrate the effects of the phase change to be mostly near F_c . Despite the cortilymph and scala-fluid+BM waves having a different phase relationship than in the base, apical BM motion still causes deflections of OHC stereocilia, OHC

elongations/contractions and cyclic cortilymph flow into the tunnels. Here we consider effects of the scala-fluid+BM and cortilymph waves in the apex.

Figure 1. The outer-hair-cell (OHC) membrane filter causes a divergence between the scala-fluid+BM traveling wave and the cortilymph wave. **Top:** The phase of OHC voltage re OHC-stereocilia current for an OHC RC filter with a corner frequency, F_c , of 3 kHz. Circles show the phase lag at BF for each waveform at bottom. **Bottom:** Snapshots of chinchilla traveling waves from tones at seven frequencies (peak-to-peak amplitudes = 1; based on ¹³). Black solid lines show scala-fluid+BM traveling waves. Red dashed lines show calculated cortilymph waves (at the point of greatest flow of cortilymph into the tunnels) offset from the scala-fluid+BM traveling wave by the delay at each BF (re the delay for $BF \gg F_c$) from an OHC-filter with an F_c of 3 kHz. For easier visualization, each wave was expanded by a factor of 2 along the horizontal axis (keeping its center at the BF place).

Strong evidence for two waves in the cochlear apex comes from auditory-nerve data, particularly cats. AN TCs from the cat apex often show two regions: a central region around the fiber's characteristic frequency (CF), and TC-edge "side-lobes" that can appear at higher (Fig. 2) or lower frequencies than the central lobe, or both^{7,14}. TCs with side lobes can be seen in other species (e.g., Macaque¹⁵). In some species (e.g., chinchilla) excitation at the TC edges may be from the same origins as cat side lobes, but the TC edge response blends into the rest of the TC (e.g.¹⁶, see below). Importantly, CF-lobes and side-lobes have different properties: compared to the CF lobe, side-lobes have shorter group delays¹⁷ and are more strongly inhibited by medial olivocochlear (MOC) efferents¹⁸ (Fig. 2).

The fact that TC side lobes have shorter group delays than the CF lobe¹⁷⁻¹⁹ (Fig. 2A), is consistent with side-lobes arising from the cortilymph wave and central-lobes arising primarily from the scala-fluid+BM wave. In Figure 1, the cortilymph wave is shifted apically relative to the scala-fluid+BM wave, which means that at a given place, the cortilymph wave arrives first and therefore has a shorter group delay. However, the difference in group delays shown in Fig. 2, left, is more than can be accounted for by the delay offset in Fig. 1, so other factors must also be involved (see below). CF lobes and side lobes are both inhibited by MOC efferents¹⁸, which shows that both receive OHC-based amplification. However, side-lobe MOC inhibition is stronger, and in some cases can almost completely remove the side lobe¹⁸ (Fig. 2B). This is consistent with the side lobe originating from the cortilymph wave, which doesn't exist without OHC cyclic contractions/expansions.

Two (or more) AN drives are also shown by the two "components" of AN-fiber rate-vs-level functions^{20,21}. Component I is seen at low levels, and separated by an abrupt phase change, component II is seen at high levels. A hypothesis consistent with the data is that component I is due the combined scala-fluid+BM and cortilymph drives (both are OHC amplified so they plateau at high levels), and component II is due to the scala-fluid+BM-wave drive at high levels where it receives little or no amplification and continues to grow above the OHC-saturation level. The drives have different phase relationships and at certain frequencies can be out of phase and cancel²⁰⁻²¹. The micromechanical processes involved in these phase relationships are not fully understood, but see ²².

Figure 2. Auditory-nerve (AN) fiber responses showing tuning curves (black, thick lines) with characteristic frequency (CF) regions and side lobes, and the relationship of these lobes to the group delay (Left), and to inhibition by stimulation of medial olivocochlear (MOC) efferents (Right). Left: data obtained with the methods of Stankovic & Guinan^{23,24}, Right: from ¹⁸.

The fact that Component I has OHC-amplified motion explains why AN fibers show two levels of firing-rate saturation. Consider Figure 3 from Gifford and Guinan²¹. In this example (done at an off-CF tone frequency where components I and II are out of phase), at low levels the OHC-amplified drive grows fast, and controls the response, but the OHC action saturates at a moderately-high level, resulting in the firing-rate plateau seen at lower levels. As sound level is increased further, the passive part of the scala-fluid+BM drive continues to grow and becomes dominant; and while this drive doesn't mechanically saturate, the IHC synapses saturate, resulting in the higher-level rate saturation. Furosemide and MOC efferents both reduce component I but not component II^{21,25}, which is consistent with component I being due to OHC-amplified responses, and component II being passive.

In chinchilla AN responses, there are not clear TC side lobes. However, chinchilla AN data are consistent with the drives being similar to those in cats, in that chinchilla AN maxim firing rates are higher for CF tones than for tones near the TC edges (see Fig. 4 of ¹⁶). A hypothesis that fits these data is that the rate saturations near CF are from the scala-fluid+BM drive which continues to grow at the highest levels so that the near-CF saturations are due to IHC-AN-synapse saturations, while rate saturations near the TC edges are from the cortilymph-fluid drive which has wider tuning and saturates at a lower level due to saturation of the OHC forces that create the cortilymph-fluid drive.

At frequencies near CF, the low-level component-I AN response has a long group delay¹⁷⁻¹⁹ (Fig. 2), consistent with the scala-fluid+BM drive dominating the co-existing cortilymph drive. But in the side lobes the shorter-group-delay cortilymph drive appears to be the only drive present because it can be MOC inhibited almost completely (Fig 2A). Evidence that the scala-fluid+BM drive is not exciting the side lobe, is that at high levels this drive cannot be MOC inhibited, whereas the side lobe can be completely inhibited.

Another line of evidence comes from AN responses to clicks. In cat AN fibers with BFs <4 kHz, the AN initial peak (ANIP) in response to rarefaction clicks is strongly inhibited by MOC efferents, and (like TC side lobes) can be almost completely abolished by MOC stimulation²⁶. Furthermore, for fibers of similar CFs, the ANIP latency is similar to the group delay measured from TC side lobes, which is evidence that they both rise from the same underlying mechanism, presumably the cortilymph wave. Side-lobe delays are shorter than TC main-lobe delays by more than the ¼ cycle offset of Fig. 1. A hypothesis to explain this, based on the ANIP response, is that the initial scala-fluid+BM wave of the click response produces OHC contractions that force cortilymph fluid to flow apically ahead of the scala-fluid+BM traveling wave, thereby producing a shorter-delay excitation in the regions reached by the cortilymph wave, i.e. the first phase of the cortilymph wave travels ahead of the first phase of the scala-fluid+BM wave. Overall, cat apical click and tone AN responses both support the hypothesis that apical AN fibers are excited by separate drives from the cortilymph-flow wave and the scala-fluid+BM wave.

Other base-to-apex differences

A change in the SFOAE delay-vs-frequency slope at mid-cochlea has been one of the defining features of the base-to-apex differences (e.g. ^{9,10}). One hypothesis is that SFOAEs arise from the cortilymph wave through the OoC area change it produces, and that the cortilymph wave has a shorter group delay than the scala-fluid+BM traveling wave apical of Fc. While this produces a change in the right direction in the SFOAE delay-vs-frequency slope, it is not large enough to account for all of the observed change in slope, or in humans, a second change in slope near 1 kHz¹⁰. Other factors must be involved, e.g., traveling-wave amplification being different in the apex than in the base.

For low-frequency (a few hundred Hz, or less) sounds, the phase that excites AN fibers reverses in the middle of the cochlea (e.g. ⁸). This shift has been attributed to a shift in whether AN fibers are excited by the traditional RL-TM shear or by an “BM-up-inhibit” drive²². It seems likely that this shift is brought about by the change in the relationship between the cortilymph and scala-fluid+BM waves that occurs at Fc. However, the detailed micromechanical changes that cause the shift are not understood.

Another base-to-apex difference is in the direction of glides¹⁰. The upward glide seen in most of the cochlea is due to wave dispersion of the traveling wave, i.e., low frequencies arrive earlier than high frequencies²⁷. The downward glide at low-BF regions is due to early excitation by a mode of motion with a below-BF resonant frequency^{28,29}. One possibility is that in the extreme apex, the earliest IHC excitation is from a cortilymph wave that was produced by more basal (lower CF region) OHCs causing an apical cortilymph flow that excites before the traveling wave.

DISCUSSION

The hypothesis that some (perhaps most) of the cochlear base-to-apex physiological differences arise from effects of the OHC RC time constant fits a wide range of data. It is the first hypothesis that explains the seemingly anomalous short group delays in the upper side-lobes of AN-fiber tuning curves¹⁷⁻¹⁹ (Fig. 2A). It should be kept in mind that Fc may be somewhat different in different species and/or may vary along the cochlear length.

Cat AN data are consistent with the hypothesis that cortilymph-wave excitation has wider tuning than excitation by scala-fluid+BM wave¹⁷⁻¹⁸. One reason may be that the two waves excite AN fibers through different micromechanical paths, and the different mechanical properties of these paths lead to different tuning. Another factor may be that the scala-fluid+BM wave is terminated by a connection between the two scalae at the helicotrema, whereas, the OoC tunnel space is closed at the extreme apex, which would influence cortilymph flow and its tuning.

Although there is now a hypothesis for traveling wave amplification that fits the data in high-BF regions³⁻⁵, there is no good mechanistic explanation for traveling-wave amplification in the low-frequency apex. It is not even clear whether the cortilymph and scala-fluid+BM waves are amplified by a single mechanism or by separate mechanisms.

Mammalian hearing at high-frequencies evolved in small mammals because head-shadow provides an important cue for sound localization³⁰. When large mammals evolved, they could use low-frequency hearing for sound localization. At frequencies below Fc, the high-frequency method for traveling-wave amplification didn't work, so a new amplification method evolved. Although there are not obvious differences in amplification across mammals with low-frequency hearing, it is possible that different methods evolved across different mammalian lines. It appears that mice didn't evolve low-frequency hearing.

We conclude that:

- At least some cochlear base-to-apex differences arise due to the change in delay from the OHC RC filter.
- Re scala-fluid+BM waves, cortilymph waves are delayed less below the 3 kHz RC corner frequency
- Scala-fluid+BM waves arise from a passive wave (the traveling wave) that is amplified, while cortilymph waves only exist due to OHC action. This leads to differences in their susceptibility to furosemide, or MOC stimulation, and whether they saturate at high sound levels.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Jong-Hoon Nam: In the first part [of the talk] you showed that cortilymph is driven by OHCs. Can you discuss the OHC – cortilymph interaction in the aspect of global amplification and local amplification?

John Guinan: I didn't quite get the question.

Jong-Hoon Nam: There's some theory regarding cochlear amplification: global amplification and local amplification [two voices at once]

John Guinan: What you are calling "global amplification", I think I am calling traveling wave amplification [I misinterpreted his meaning of "global amplification" – see below]. Wherever there is motion of the Organ of Corti, [with the BM] pushing up, you get bending of the [OHC] stereocilia and you get contraction of the OHCs. And only in the narrow region, when its [the BM and OoC motion] is in the short-wave region do you get an [OoC] area change and therefore amplification of the traveling wave.

Jong-Hoon Nam: So your explanation, somehow, in my understanding, is more relevant to local amplification. Global amplification is the entire cochlear traveling wave.

John Guinan: What do you mean by "global amplification"?

Jong-Hoon Nam: Along the length of the traveling wave, it accumulates energy to amplify only at the peak. This is global amplification as I understand it.

John Guinan: [Throughout the long-wave region there is amplification of motion at the bottom of the OHCs, without accumulation in the traveling wave] I call that local amplification. It is not coupled to the traveling wave. It is just acting at a local place. That's why your term "global" amplification [is confusing].

Jong-Hoon Nam: Probably there is some clear definition we can share.

Sunil Puria (moderator): Perhaps we can come back to this in the Discussion.

John Guinan *post meeting clarification:* I think the term "global amplification" was first used by He et al (2018, *Elife* 7. doi:10.7554/eLife.37625) in an attempt to understand their measurements that showed that at a wide range of frequencies far below BF, that motion of some OoC structure above the BM was much larger than BM motion, and therefore there was widespread motion "amplification". Consistent with the idea that this far-below-BF amplification must be doing something useful, their speculation was that this much-greater-than-BM motion somehow led to a global action that produced amplification of the traveling wave, even though amplification was seen in BM motion only near BF. However, a physical manifestation of this (either as a slow wave or a fast wave) has never been found experimentally. Amplification of the motion response to a tone is, indeed, widespread along the cochlea, but saying that it has a "global" effect is not correct – it does not produce an action at a distance, and it doesn't produce a pressure wave (fast or slow). I think the term "global amplification" has no physical meaning and therefore is misleading and should be dropped.

At frequencies far below BF, motion that is many dB larger than BM motion, as found by He et al (similar motion has been reported to be at the OHC-Deiters-cell junction in studies that were able to image the OoC structures during the measurements) is what I have called "non-propagating amplification" (Guinan, 2022). I now prefer the term "local amplification". It is local because it does not couple to the traveling wave (because it produces no OoC area change). The assessment that this amplification doesn't propagate along the cochlea has been shown by experiments using suppression by a second tone (Dewey et al., 2019. *Journal of neuroscience*. 39, 1805-1816; Fallah, et al. 2019. *Hearing research* 377, 271-281; Fallah, et al. 2021. *Hear Res* 405, 108234). and by apex-to-base perfusion of OHC-deactivating drugs (Goodman et al., 2020. *Biophys J* 118, 1183-1195).

In contrast, "traveling-wave amplification", which is manifest in the amplification of BM motion, is produced in the short-wave region where the OHCs produce an OoC area change that allows RL net transverse motion to be greater than BM net transverse motion. It is still an open question as to how far basal of CF is the extent of the OHC motion that produces an OoC area change that leads to traveling-wave amplification. However, as shown by the many measurements of the extent of amplification of BM motion, it seems unlikely that the local amplification that is seen at frequencies (or locations) many octaves below BF, produces changes to the traveling wave that are big enough to say that amplification accumulates throughout the traveling wave. Current evidence indicates that

amplification accumulates only within ½ to 1 octave basal of BF, and there is no “global amplification” of the traveling wave.

Jont Allen (after talk): So we all agree, I agree, you agree, that there is a change in the sensitivity of the hair cells depending on whether the efferent system is on or off.

John Guinan: The outer hair cells are modulated by efferents, and ...

{ Guinan and Allen talking overlapping and interleaved in the next few lines, especially near “sensitivity” }

Jont Allen: Yes. It changes the gain.

John Guinan (continuing):... activating the efferents effectively produces less motion for a given bending of stereocilia.

Jont Allen: There is a change in the sensitivity.

John Guinan:...in the motion output

Jont Allen: The sensitivity of the hair cells is modified by ...

John Guinan: I don't like the term “sensitivity” there.

Jont Allen: Well, I'm trying to use the word “sensitivity”. I'm making up the word, not you. So... I'm asking you if you agree that the sensitivity has changed when the efferent system ... the sensitivity... The signal level depends on the inner hair cell response. And obviously, the outer hair cells, which are affected by the efferent system, control how much the inner hair cells see. So, my question is why does it have to be a power gain? Or, why does it have to be an amplification? Why can't the thing with the most sensitive case ... why isn't that just the natural state and when you turn on the efferents it reduces the response? I mean, Why does it have to be a gain, instead of an attenuation? I don't see the logic there.

John Guinan, *post meeting clarification:* Statements like “the outer hair cells, which are affected by the efferent system, control how much the inner hair cells see” have imbedded in them incorrect assumptions about how the cochlea works. The OHCs do not control what fraction of the motion the IHCs see, they control the actual motion (e.g. BM motion, see Guinan and Cooper, 2008, JASA 124:1080). My answer (below) focused on what I think was Jont's main question: Is there true *cochlear-amplifier gain*, i.e., energy injected into the system by active processes that increases motion responses.

John Guinan: OK, well...I think it is actually easier to talk about that [whether there is gain in the cochlea] in the context of what happens in the long-wave region [i.e., at frequencies or locations that are more than an octave below the best BF]. In the long-wave region, the current measurements have shown that the biggest motion (in a live, good preparation) is at the bottom of the outer hair cells (OHCs). The bottom of the OHCs move, typically 15 dB, or so, more than the basilar membrane (BM), and the reticular-lamina motion is not much different than BM motion. When you kill the animal that [the increased motion at the OHC bottoms compared to BM motion] goes away and the BM motion pretty much stays the same. The motion [in the dead animal] is just passive. And so [in a normal live animal far below BF] you have this huge amount of motion in the middle of the cochlea [in the middle of the organ of Corti], and it is really hard to see that that's [the large motion at the bottom of the OHCs, is] coming from the energy traveling in from the stapes [via the traveling wave]. It is due to some local source that's producing energy that's making the motion.

Jont Allen (off mike and barely audible): When the animal dies, you see a difference and you are interpreting that saying it must be amplification.

John Guinan: I'm calling amplification, bigger motion due to these active processes. And that they [active processes] must be, therefore, putting in cycle by cycle energy to make the cycle-by-cycle motion bigger.

John Guinan, *post meeting clarification:* Jont focuses on the change with death, but this is not an important part of the argument that the OHC-bottom movement in the far-below-CF region shows *amplification* (which is why I chose to consider motion in the long-wave region for my answer). In the normal, living animal, the motion in the middle of the organ of Corti, at the bottom of OHCs is much larger than the BM motion or the RL motion, despite it being in between these lower-amplitude motions. How can this happen if motion in the cochlea is only caused by the motion following the traveling wave? The traveling wave applies a pressure difference across the cochlear

partition and that pressure difference, acting primarily on BM stiffness, causes an overall transverse motion of the organ of Corti. Significantly, in a normal, live animal in the far-below-CF region, the motion at the bottom of the OHCs is much greater than the BM or RL motions, so that the OHC-bottom motion cannot be simply following the overall motion of the cochlear partition. Jont's implied hypothesis is that there is no increased motion of cochlear structures due to active processes; there is only increased damping that reduces motion. This does not explain the much greater motion at the bottom of the OHCs relative to the BM and the RL. The hypothesis I gave at the beginning of my talk (see Guinan, 2022, Hearing Res) provides an explanation consistent with these data, namely that BM motion leads to cyclic deflections of OHC stereocilia, which produces cyclic changes in OHC length that (in the long-wave region) lead to motion at the bottom of the OHCs that is increased (or "amplified") by OHC active processes relative to BM and RL motion.

Sunil Puria (moderator): Lets have the last question.

Kuni Iwasa: I'm interested in [the] higher end of frequency. You know, lower frequency travels some distance, but [at the] very high end of auditory frequencies, [does] the same thing apply?

John Guinan: When you are above CF, you mean?

Kuni Iwasa: Yes. At highest CF. Is the situation the same [as at low CFs]?

Sunil Puria (moderator): What he is asking is: high frequencies are more basal, low frequencies are apical. The travel time difference, is [that] the difference in processing?

John Guinan: The outline, I gave is for cochlear amplification of the traveling wave [in the high-CF region]. I didn't really talk a lot about the low frequency part of that [traveling wave amplification]. [My talk started with an outline of] how cochlear amplification of the traveling-wave works in the base. That is a set body of theory that I think fits all together. How that gets translated to the apex, I really don't know. I don't think it's simply translated to the apex [with nothing changed].

John Guinan, *post meeting clarification:* I think the thrust of Kuni's question may have been to ask if the differences in cochlear *travel distances* between low-CF and high-CF regions is an important factor in cochlear amplification; my answer is "I think not". What is important for the action of OHC in producing traveling wave amplification versus just producing local amplification is whether the location of the OHC contractions are in the long-wave or short-wave region. For lower CFs, the long-wave region extends over a much greater distance than for higher CFs. But since only local amplification is produced in the long-wave region (not gain accumulation that increases the traveling wave energy) the greater long-wave distance makes little or no difference for the traveling wave amplification (at least for CFs above Fc). The accumulation of traveling-wave amplification takes place only in the short-wave region where OHCs produce an organ-of-Corti area change that allows the RL net transverse motion to locally be greater than the BM net transverse motion.

François Deloche (*from Canvas entry*): In the abstract, you write: 'In the base, recent data show that amplification of the traveling wave does not come from outer-hair-cell (OHC) forces acting on the basilar membrane (BM). Instead, it comes from OHCs producing cyclic cortilymph flow along the organ-of-Corti (OoC) tunnels (...)' I think you would want to make clear that these statements are still hypotheses. The same remark applies to other parts of the text. E.g., page 3 'strong evidence for two waves in the cochlear apex...' I would be a bit more conservative.

John Guinan: I think the data clearly demonstrate that traveling wave amplification does NOT come from OHC forces acting on the BM – at least in the regions where the measurements have been made in the base. So this is not a hypothesis, it has been demonstrated by experiments. I agree that the new theory is a hypothesis so I changed the text, to say that is a hypothesis. "Strong evidence" is correct, i.e., it does not say the evidence is "compelling".

François Deloche: You estimate the RC filter corner frequency to be 3 kHz (in gerbils). I have seen other work suggesting that Fc instead changes with position on the cochlea (e.g. Rabbitt and Bidone, 2023). How can we conciliate these two characterizations?

John Guinan: In the Discussion I acknowledge that Fc may vary with species and along the cochlear length. This needs more Fc data. The possible variation of Fc cannot be settled by theory.

François Deloche: On the two components of AN rate functions: is that related to the phenomenon of ‘peak splitting’? What do you think of the recent proposal that it could be explained by the auditory nerve being mechanically sensitive at high sound levels? (Perez-Flores et al. 2022)?

John Guinan: There is an indirect connection between the two components and “peak splitting” (see the Lin & Guinan papers cited below). I am very skeptical about there being significant direct mechanical excitation of Auditory nerve fibers from sound at non-traumatic levels. Lin T, Guinan JJ, Jr. (2000). *J Acoust Soc Am* 107:2615-2630. Lin T, Guinan JJ, Jr. (2004) *J Acoust Soc Am* 116 (1):405-416

François Deloche: You are showing the effect of the MOCR on low-frequency tuning with AN tuning curves, which illustrates perfectly the peculiarities of AN responses at the cochlear apex. Do we have an idea if ‘regular’ compressive non-linearities, i.e. the sound-level dependence of gain and tuning, affects cochlear tuning the same way? (Or if they differ, then it could tell something on how the amplification mechanism is altered differently by MOCR or sound-level).

John Guinan: I think the idea that there are “regular compressive non-linearities” in the apex (that are similar to those in the base) is too simplistic. In the apex, there are (at least) two different mechanical drives that mix and produce responses, and these have different growth functions and different delays (in part because of the OHC RC time constant affecting the different drives in different ways). Their interaction can produce complex results (e.g., sometimes cancellations in the drive to IHCs, but only at certain frequencies re CF).

François Deloche: I was a bit confused on the change in SFOAE delays that you mention at the end of the paper. If I am correct, the SFOAE delays are more substantial at low frequencies, while the title of your paper indicates that cortilymph waves are delayed less at the apex. Does not that go in opposite directions?

John Guinan: The slopes of SFOAE vs frequency functions go up or down, and the amount of delay produced by the RC filter, depend on how the delay is expressed: in time units or tone periods. In either case, if the slope of a line that matches SFOAE delays at frequencies >3 kHz is extended to frequencies <3 kHz, this predicts a longer delay than is measured. See: Christensen, Abdala & Shera (2020).

François Deloche: At the end, you also mention a change of phase or low-frequency excitation in the middle of the cochlea. I went to see that paper you are referring to, where it is written that ‘Since a low-frequency bias tone suppresses responses to CF tones at approximately the same phase for all CFs, gross cochlear motion must not be reversing at mid-cochlear CFs. Instead, it appears that the mix of IHC drives changes in the middle of the cochlea, which means that some aspects of cochlear micromechanics that affect the fluid flow past IHC stereocilia must change in mid-cochlea.’ Would that mean that cortilymph-wave primarily affect[s] the fluid motion near IHCs (and not the BM traveling-wave)?

John Guinan: No. Both the traveling wave and the cortilymph wave can produce OoC structural motions (e.g., of the RL) and the *mixture* of these motions produces the IHC excitation. The base-to-apex change is more likely to be a change from classic RL-TM shear driving the IHC stereocilia, to RL-TM gap changes causing fluid flow that drives the IHC stereocilia (see Guinan, 2012).

George Samaras (from Canvas entry): In the section titled "WHAT CAUSES BASE-TO-APEX DIFFERENCES?", you mention that for high-BF, the OHC phase is 'wrong', i.e. it cannot add energy to the traveling wave via the BM, and instead does so by pumping energy into the scala media via the RL and/or TM. At low-BF (BF $<$ cutoff frequency), the OHC phase is such that it can add energy via the BM. If I understand correctly, you are in effect suggesting two different mechanisms of fluid-BM traveling wave amplification at the base and apex, respectively. How does this fit with recent experimental evidence that the Deiters' cell bodies are of similar compliance to the OHCs (Dewey et al. 2021, Zhou et al. 2022), which challenges the possibility of adding energy to the traveling wave via the bottom end of the OHCs to the fluid-BM traveling wave? You also mention that at the apex "the OHC long axis is closer to parallel to the BM," further challenging addition of energy via the bottom of the OHCs.

John Guinan: I think it is likely that there are different mechanisms that produce traveling-wave amplification in the apex than in the base. I did not propose that ‘OHCs acting on the BM through Deiters cells’ is the main source of traveling wave amplification in the apex, only that it cannot be ruled out as having a role.

George Samaras: The shorter delay of the cortilymph wave (compared to the delay of the fluid-BM traveling wave) at the apex is a great explanation for the change in slope in SFOAE delay vs. frequency that is observed in multiple species. Shera and Altoe recently looked at the possible effects of the Y-shaped cytoarchitecture formed by the Deiters' cell bodies, the OHCs, and the phalangeal processes (Shera and Altoe 2023). They concluded that the ratios of SFOAE to BM delays are more compatible with primarily local forces, and not non-local forces that arise from the Y-shaped geometry. They looked at high-frequency data ($BF > F_c$) in their analysis. Is it possible that at low frequencies, the change in SFOAE delay slope is explained by a greater relative effect of non-local forces? Could it be that both the shorter delay of the cortilymph wave, as you propose, and the variability in the degree of non-local forces are both pieces of the puzzle in understanding differences in SFOAE delays between the base and apex?

John Guinan: Yes, I think that non-local forces that come from the cortilymph wave are what is happening in the apex to produce SFOAE delays that are shorter than expected.